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SYMPTOMS AND MANIFESTATION OF INSECT PESTS IN SUNFLOWER

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ABSTRACT

Sunflower (Helianthus annuus L.) is one of the most essential oil seed crops and potentially fits into India 's agricultural system and oil production field. Various diseases, insects and nematodes assault destroy the sunflower crop, lead to a wide range of production and yield losses. Sunflower is vulnerable to different kinds of diseases. The most severe sunflower diseases are caused by fungi. The magnitude of these diseases affects crop yields. The account of significant sunflower pests has been addressed for a brief understanding of low sunflower crop yields in India

Keywords: Fungi, nematodes, Oil crop pests, sunflower, fungal parasites, insect damage

INTRODUCTION:

Sunflower (*Helianthus annuus L.*) is popularly known as "Surajmukhi" as it observes the movement of the sun. The name derived from the Greek word "Helios" means "Sun" and "Anthois" means "flower" (Heiser, 1951). Sunflower is a major oilseed crop in India. Most of today's varieties are cultivated all over the world. In India, Sunflower crop was started in early in 1969. sunflower is grown over a 0.52 m ha area with an output of 0.34 million tonnes and a productivity of 643 kg per hectare in India (Anon., 2016).

The sunflower is one of the world's most essential edible oilseed crops for soybeans and groundnuts. It is an essential source of oil which is edible and nutritious. Nearly any portion of the sunflower has commercial value. It is used in the manufacture of coatings, resins, fibres, soap and cosmetics. Oil cake is rich in protein of high quality (40-44 per cent) and is used as feed for cattle and poultry. Several biotic and abiotic stresses influence it.

INSECT PESTS

At different stages of crop growth, sunflowers are invaded by a variety of insect pests. Most pests are not sunflower specific and derive in the soil from other crops, weed hosts or plant residues. Several species of soil-dwelling insects attack sunflower seeds and seedlings, causing plant stands to become thinner or totally lost. As damaged sunflower seedlings lack the ability to regrow or tiller, sunflowers are more vulnerable to seedling damage than other field crops.

Susceptibility to insect pests and diseases are major constraints among several biotic stresses for good sunflower production. A variety of insect pests are attacking the crop and as many as 251 insect species are known to attack this crop worldwide (Rajmohan,1976). Capitulum borer *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hübner), green semilooper *Thysanoplusia orichalcea* Fab., Bihar hairy caterpillar *Spilosoma obliqua* (Walker), tobacco caterpillar *Spodoptera litura* (Fab.) and cutworm *Agrotis* sp. are the main insect pests associated with this crop in India. *Amrasca biguttula biguttula* (Basappa,1995) with green leaf hopper.

It is estimated that the loss in seed yield due to these pests is about 24.9 per cent (Anonymous, 2013). Sucking pests, such as whiteflies, leafhoppers and thrips, lead to major crop losses. In general, sucking pests occur at the early stage of the crop and their damage continues until the grain filling stage. Leaf hopper causes a substantial loss of 46% among all sucking pests (Anon., 1997), thrips are involved in the transmission of sunflower bud necrosis virus (Chander Rao, 2002) and whiteflies are of primary importance that pose a threat to the crop under favourable conditions, which do not cause direct harm but indirectly cause enormous loss as a vector of viral disease (Govindappa et al., 2011)

Objective

The present study is an analysis of Indian research results on Sunflower disease and a brief comprehension of diseases.

CHARCOAL ROT

Sunflower plants suffer from *Macrophomina phaseolina*-induced charcoal rot disease (Jalaluddin, 2008). *M. Phaseolina* has a large range of host species and is responsible for the loss of more than 500 species of cultivated and wild plants (Khan, 2007).

Study on various sunflower rots was reviewed by Ahmad (1988). There are six rots known to occur, including charcoal rot, head rot, stalk rot, collar rot, black rot and bacterial rot. Charcoal is considered the most prevalent of these. Ataga and Akueshi (1986) noted that it was *M. Phaseolina* grew well on the seeds, increased the free fatty acid and oil content and caused the oil to discolour. However, the relationship between the pathogen carried by the sunflower and the volume and consistency of the oil is not well known. *M. In* sunflower crops, *phaseolina* is recorded as the most destructive and important in yield (Mirza and Beg, 1983; Mirza, 1984).

Symptoms

There are no visible early signs of the disease, but the most common symptom is sudden wilting of plants, usually after pollination. The diseased plants mature early and show on stem brown to dark brown spots from which the disease is called 'charcoal rot' when the infected stem is broken, black microsclerotia is found in the pith. The plants become thin, dry and show stem decoloration of light grey or ashy black. It is possible to see poorly filled heads and dry stalks, which have typically become discoloured. Pith disintegrates and shredded vascular fibres emerge, coated with tiny bodies of fungal disease

SCLEROTINIA STALK WILT AND HEAD ROT

The causative agent of stalk and head rot in sunflower is *sclerotinia sclerotiorum* (Mirza and Yasmin, 1984; Bhutta et al . , 1995). This disease is present all over the world where sunflowers are grown. Seedling, stalk and head rots of

Sclerotinia sclerotiorum are a worldwide danger to sunflower (Mesterhazy and Gulya, 1988). The serious risk to sunflower growers is sunflower diseases, especially head rot, followed by charcoal rot (Mehdi and Mehdi, 1988; Khan et al . , 1999). No commercial sunflower cultivars with resistance to M have been recorded to date. Phaseolina (Gul et al., 1989; Hafeez and Ahmad, 1997; Khan, 2007; Ahmed and Burney, 1990).

Symptoms

Diseases occur in various stages, such as root rot, stem rot, and head rot. On the taproot and fibrous stems, water-soaked lesions manifest. Sudden wilting of the leaves is also marked by the disease. At the base or in other areas of the stem, grey to brown lesions appear. The plant is wilting and drying up. On drying, the stems shred into vascular strands and become straw-colored. In head rot, development of the fungus with white mycelium is observed. The pathogen 's white, fluffy mycelium can also be found under damp conditions within or outside infected tissues. Sclerotia, with or without crop residue, can live on the soil for several years. These heads are dropping off and have no seeds

ALTERNARIA BLIGHT

Alternaria blight is one of the most common and serious sunflower diseases and can become epiphytotic (Mirza and Beg, 1983). Alternaria blight has been identified by many workers as a severe disease (Ghafoor and Khan, 1974; Mirza and Ahmad, 1982; Mirza and Yasmin, 1983; Ahmad, 1988; Bhutta et al . , 1993). Spp. alternaria. It was first identified as a pathogen of the sunflower (Sackston, 1978) and has been found in most parts of the world since then, and in some years it has been destructive. A. The leaf, stem and head spotting pathogen, helianthi, tends to be the most harmful (Sackston, 1978). In order to reduce seed and oil yield by 27 to 80 percent and 17 to 33 percent respectively, Alternaria leaf spots have been identified (Reddy and Gupta, 1977; Balasubrahmanyam and Kolte, 1980). The number of seeds per head, followed by yield, is the damage resulting from the disease. It also influences seed quality by adversely influencing the vigour of the seedlings' seed germination. Such diseases are also recorded in India as major limiting factors in the development of sunflowers (Mirza and Beg, 1983; Blinda et al., 1993; Bhutta et al . , 1995).

Symptoms

The symptoms first appear on the lower leaves in the form of dark-brown to black, circular to oval-shaped spots. The spots are surrounded by necrotic chlorotic zones with concentric circles marked with a grey white necrotic centre. The disease spreads to the middle and the upper leaves gradually. Late in the season, on petioles, stems, and ray-florets, elongated spots are found, resulting in leaf blight and often causing stem and head rot. The pathogens prefer high humidity

SEPTORIA LEAF SPOTS

Henry and Gilbert (1924) first observed the Septoria leaf spot on sunflower and subsequently reported from several countries around the world, including India with a different climate zone (Siddique and Yasmeen, 1982). The sunflower has also been identified as a pathogen (Akhtar and Mirza, 1988). S. In different parts of the globe, helianthi has been reported causing yield reduction.

Symptoms

On average, 5-8% of plants exhibit signs of leaf spots. On the lower leaves, plants display tiny irregular spots that eventually spread to the upper leaves. The spots mostly originate from the leaf margins, coalescing resulting in

yellow to dark brown irregular blotches forming. On the upper leaf surface, brown to dark brown spots develop from small angular to more or less circular or often diamond-shaped, and lighter grey brown on the lower leaf surface. Many tiny pycnidia are formed in these locations on both surfaces of leaves under wet conditions. First on the lower and eventually spread to the upper leaves, a spot coalesces and leaves wither and dry (Hamid and Jalaluddin, 2007).

RHIZOPUS HEAD ROT

Three species of Rhizopus cause head rot of sunflower (*Helianthus annuus*) around the world:

R. Oryzae Went & Prinsen Geerligs (*R. nodosus* Namyslowski and *R. arrhizus* A. Fischer synanamorphs), *R. Tiegh's microsporus.*, and *R. (Ehrenb.:Fr.) Vuill, Stolonifer.* (*R. nigricans* Ehrenb's synanamorph.). Head feeding is associated with the severity of Rhizopus head rot by larvae of many insect species (Klisiewicz, 1979; Rogers et al . , 1978). *M. Rhizopus* spp. and *Phaseolina* (charcoal rot).

Symptoms

The head turns brown and develops later into smooth, grey mycelial development. At the back of the head, brown irregular water-soaked spots emerge. These spots extend, turn brown and become pulpy and soft. Heads seem abnormal, obviously. Wet weather favours the production of diseases after flowering, particularly if the heads are damaged by hail, birds, or insects. While varieties with upright heads are more often infected than varieties with bending heads, there is no control.

VERTICILLIUM WILT

A persistent soilborne and seedborne fungus, *Verticillium dahliae*, is caused by verticillium wilt, which persists in the soil for many years. On lighter soils with a history of sunflower cropping, verticillium wilt can be a serious disease. An infection occurs when sunflower roots are germinated and penetrated by soilborne microsclerotia. The fungus spreads into the vascular system of the plant, creating multiple microsclerotia that spread across the entire vascular system and all parts of the plant.

Symptoms

On individual plants or groups of plants in a field, verticillium wilt symptoms can occur. Symptoms of illness first occur on older plants, usually after the six-leaf stage. On leaves, which are gradually expanded and coalesce, prominent yellow inter-veinal patches appear, while leaf centres turn brown and necrotic, providing a mottled appearance. Affected leaves become dry easily and die. Symptoms are typically not seen before flowering, but they may occur as early as the six-leaf process under extreme conditions. Masses of small black fruiting bodies (microsclerotia) within the stalk may be present in highly diseased plants. Such microsclerotia are like finely ground pepper. The microsclerotias are irregular to club-shaped (0.1 mm or less in length) when strongly magnified. They have black streaky patches on the affected stems, and roots are also impacted. Plants display stunting, small flower heads, and root system destruction.

RUST

Sunflower rust, caused by *Puccinia helianthi* Schwein., is a major disease in the world's sunflower growing areas (*Helianthus annuus* L.) (Quresh and Jan, 1993). Rust disease has been reported, but there is no detailed information

on disease occurrence and distribution in different agro-ecological areas. Sunflower oil yield losses caused by rust infection are significantly affected by the growth stage of the plant when infection occurs and the severity of infection (Siddiqui and Brown, 1997).

Symptoms

On the lower leaves, thin, chestnut brown or orange to black powdery, dispersed pustules appear first. But it can stretch to all the leaves, and even to the living parts of the head. Pre-mature leaves become dry, affecting yield and seed quality. The leaves can turn yellow, but on the plants they seldom fall. On voluntary seedlings, the first pycnial and aecial infections usually occur, rising among the debris of the previous crop. The inoculum is dispersed by wind from the affected crop.

DOWNY MILDEW

Sunflower Downy mildew disease has been known to be a highly harmful disease. Primarily by seeds, this disease has spread to all sunflower growing countries (Viranyi, 1990). Downy mildew, because of its systemic form of infection, is a significant obstacle to sunflower production. One of the main sunflower diseases (Rahim et al . , 2002) is the sunflower downy mildew caused by *Plasmopara halstedii*. The most damaging ones are *Plasmopara halstedii* (Farl.) Berl and de Toni. *P. halstedii* is a soil-borne pathogen and, for young sunflower seedlings, its oospores serve as the primary inoculum. The disease has mainly been spread to all sunflower growing nations by seed (Leppik, 1966; Viranyi, 1990).

Symptoms

Depending on tissue age, inoculum level, environmental conditions, and cultivar reaction, *P. halstedii* can induce disease symptoms of various types. Damping-off of seedlings are the key symptoms; systemic stem leaf and flower / seed head infection, which is the most typical and significant; cotyledon-limited systemic infection (Ljubich and Gulya, 1988); localised root and/or hypocotyl under-ground infection; localised leaf infections that cause angular leaf spotting. As seedlings and mature plants, the downy mildew fungus assaults sunflowers, triggering white cottony growth in the young plants, and big, clublike roots and stunted growth in the older ones.

WHITE FLIES

This is a major sunflower pest. It usually tends to be extremely polyphagous from November to February. In Andhra Pradesh , Telangana, Karnataka , Tamil Nadu and Maharastra, it is a severe pest. He found it all year round in Tamil Nadu.

Life cycle

Oval, scale-like nymphs remain attached to the surface of the leaf. Adults are tiny, moth-like, covered with milky white waxy powder with a yellowish body and wings. On the lower surface of the leaves, eggs are laid separately. Eggs hatch in the space of around a week. On the lower surface of the leaves, the nymph stage remains attached and takes about 4 weeks to complete growth. The number of generations each year ranges between 12-15.

Damage

The sap is normally sucked by nymphs and adults from the underside of the leaves and honeydew is excreted. Infestation provides a platform for black moulds to grow. Later, when the attack is serious, the plant's vitality is

diminished. Sickly leaves appear and get covered with sooty mould. It also transmits the leaf curl virus, stunted plant growth, shedding of fruit bodies.

Whitefly Insect Pest of Sunflower

Whitefly has recently emerged in Northern Karnataka, India as the latest potential sucking sunflower insect pest and also serves as the leaf curl begomovirus vector. This has drawn a great deal of attention from entomologists and pathologists as it affects the productivity of the country's sunflower and significant oilseed crop (Katti, 2007).

In the sunflower growing areas of the northern districts of Karnataka, the whitefly infestation has been noted in endemic form consecutively for the last three years. The magnitude of the disease ranged from 10% to 58% and, correspondingly, the increased population of B. With an average of 14.7 B, tabaci (up to 200 per leaf) was observed. In both open pollinated varieties and hybrids, tabaci per leaf.

CONCLUSION

Among the different insecticides tested, diafenthiuron 50 percent WP @ 1 g / l reported significantly less whitefly population (12.00 and 10.53 whitefly per plant after first and second spray, respectively) followed by triazophos 40 percent EC @ 2 ml / l (12.49 and 11.32 whitefly per plant after first and second spray, respectively).

The next best treatment was flonicamide 50 percent WG @ 0.4 g / l (16.26 and 13.81 whitefly per plant after first and second spray, respectively), which was 5 percent SC @ 1 ml / l on par fipronil (16.57 and 13.75 whitefly per plant after first and second spray, respectively), followed by buprofezine 25 percent SC @ 1 ml / l (17.06 and 14.47 whitefly per plant after first and second spray, respectively). Up to seven days after spraying, the chemicals proved to be successful.

These treatments were accompanied by 50 percent WG clothianidin, 50 percent EC profenophos and 0.03 percent azadirachtin. Untreated management registered the highest population of pests. The present results were in accordance with Kharel et al. (2016), who stated that the most promising treatment in reducing the whitefly population was diafenthiuron 50 WP @ 312 g a.i./ha.

Correspondingly, Dhaka (2016) recorded that the treatment was found to be very effective against sucking pests with spiromesifen 240 SC @ 150 ml.a.i./ha and diafenthiuron 50 WP @ 312.5 g a.i./ha. Gopal Das and Tarikul Islam (2014) stated that against Jassids and whiteflies, fipronil and buprofezin proved to be superior. Sanjeev Kumar and Gill (2010) also announced that triazophos 40 EC @ 1.0 l / ha registered the lowest whitefly population at 3.67 / plant as compared to 10.99 / plant in control.

Likewise, Kumar et al. (2001) recorded that triazophos 0.05 percent was found to be superior in controlling the brinjal whitefly population and resulted in a population reduction of 75.22 percent over control. A significantly higher seed yield of 1346 and 1301 kg / ha was reported in diafenthiuron 50 percent WP @ 1 g / l and triazophos 40 percent EC @ 2 ml / l and triazophos 40 percent EC @ 2 ml / l.

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